

A Probabilistic Ensemble Framework for Evapotranspiration: Spatiotemporal Error Structure Outperforms Calibration Complexity: supplemental document

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This document provides technical details supporting the main manuscript, including: field data quality control and gap-filling procedures (S1-S2), footprint analysis (S3), temporal upscaling methods (S4), ensemble benchmark justification (S5), complete Bayesian model specifications (S6-S8), and model diversity assessment (S9). Stan implementations are available via the Data availability statement.

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1. S1: QUALITY ASSURANCE AND QUALITY CONTROL (QA/QC)

A multi-tiered quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC) framework, based on established eddy covariance and micrometeorological protocols [1–3], guided field operations, sensor calibration, high-frequency data processing, and block-averaged flux derivation. Field operations included monthly sensor cleaning, leveling verification, instrument orientation checks, and weekly monitoring for prompt component replacement. Manufacturer-recommended wind speed-dependent adjustments were applied to net radiation. Meteorological data validation adapted standard frameworks [4, Appendix D], incorporating physical limit checks (e.g., relative humidity between 0-100%) and statistical outlier detection [5]. Solar elevation angles were calculated to align sensor measurements with logged data, and temporal consistency was verified by graphical comparison with two nearby reference stations [6]. Soil heat flux (G) calculations incorporated heat storage terms using field-measured bulk density. Site-specific, expert verified anomaly detection was performed yearly for heat flux plates, soil temperature (Tsoil), and volumetric water content (VWC). Spatially representative G was derived by averaging replicate sensors between crop rows and beneath canopy. Missing Tsoil values (≤ 30 min gaps) were imputed using correlated co-located sensors or linear interpolation. VWC underwent secondary recalibration against maximum annual soil saturation, with site-specific period means replacing anomalous values. High-frequency (10 Hz) turbulence data underwent automated spike detection and removal, followed by standard double rotation to aligned coordinate systems with mean wind vectors, ensuring zero mean vertical and lateral wind components over 30-minute periods [7, 8]. For 30-minute averaged covariances and meteorological variables, comprehensive outlier

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detection used dataset-wide Z-score screening with asymmetric thresholds: +6 to +20 SD (upper) and -5 to -20 SD (lower) for covariances; ± 0.25 to ± 8 SD for meteorological variables. Nocturnal solar radiation noise ($R_s > 0 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ when solar elevation $< 0^\circ$) was removed. Moving average filters (49-period/ 1 day and 25-period/ 12 hours windows) with symmetric cut-offs ($\geq \pm 3.0$ SD) minimized false positives. Sensible heat flux (H) quality control compared double-rotation-corrected (H_{DR}) versus raw coordinate (H_{raw}) values, flagging data if $|H_{DR} - H_{raw}| > 45 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ and H_{DR}/H_{raw} ratios were outside 0.5-2.0. Additional Z-score analysis used moving averages with magnitude-dependent thresholds: ± 2.8 SD for $|H| > 300 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ (25-period window) and ± 3.2 SD for $|H| > 350 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ (49-period window). Final expert manual review addressed remaining physically implausible values. All data gaps were filled with standardized missing data flags, and all procedures were designed to ensure consistency and compliance with global flux network standards [3].

2. S2: DATA GAP-FILLING

Following the rigorous QA/QC protocol, we implemented a conservative data-driven gap-filling methodology to ensure reliable time series continuity. This approach, leveraging machine learning techniques, was systematically applied across all micrometeorological variables and energy balance components to maintain consistency in the resulting dataset. Machine learning models derive functional relationships directly from observational data, unconstrained by predefined physical equations. These models are significantly influenced by data preprocessing, predictor variable selection, data density, and model-specific configurations including hyperparameter optimization. Despite widespread adoption for filling gaps in Eddy Covariance systems [9–14], standardization of ML gap-filling practices remains challenging due to this inherent complexity. To navigate this complexity and ensure methodological rigor, our implementation was guided by eight key principles distilled from recent flux methodology literature, including comprehensive reviews like [15] and comparative studies such as [16]: (1) maximizing the temporal extent of training datasets to capture seasonal and interannual variability; (2) prioritizing high-quality in situ measurements as primary predictors; (3) recognizing that feature selection significantly impacts model performance; (4) acknowledging the consistently strong performance of decision tree-based ensemble models; (5) understanding that separate model training for daytime and nighttime data is unnecessary; (6) leveraging the capability of ML approaches to effectively fill gaps up to two months, significantly outperforming standard statistical techniques which often degrade after approximately 12 days; (7) noting that while performance generally decreases with increasing gap length, differences remain statistically insignificant for gaps under 30 days; and (8) emphasizing that hyperparameter optimization is essential for achieving optimal model performance. Based on these principles and extensive evidence, we selected gradient boosted trees (GBT) [17] for their well-documented strong performance in flux gap-filling across various ecosystem types [15, 16, 18–22] and their inherent resistance to overfitting via ensemble aggregation [23]. Our implementation featured automated hyperparameter optimization using a randomized grid search to minimize operator bias and ensure model optimality. Concurrently, an automated feature engineering process performed both selection of the most informative original predictors and systematic generation of interaction and transformation features. This combined approach effectively constrained model complexity, mitigated overfitting risks, and captured non-linear flux responses and inherent temporal dependencies. We implemented a sequential gap-filling procedure designed to maximize the availability of predictive features while minimizing imbalances in temporal data density. Initial imputation targeted primary meteorological variables (air temperature) using redundant measurements from proximal meteorological stations, first processing each station independently before leveraging multi-source prediction. Subsequently, we gap-filled energy balance components - net radiation and soil heat flux - incorporating both the previously completed meteorological time series and auxiliary station data as predictors. The final stage addressed sensible heat flux gaps, utilizing the complete suite of meteorological and previously gap-filled flux variables as input features. Despite robust evidence supporting machine learning methods' efficacy for gaps extending up to 60 days, we adopted a conservative threshold, restricting imputation to gaps not exceeding six consecutive observations (3.0 hours). This constraint prioritizes data integrity by minimizing the risk of introducing artificial patterns or systematic bias that could emerge from imputing extended periods with no observational constraints.

3. S3: FOOTPRINT ANALYSIS MAPS

This section presents the daily weighted averaged flux footprint climatologies for the study sites derived using the FFP model [24]. The visualizations illustrate the spatial extent of the source areas contributing to the measured scalar fluxes (Latent Heat, Sensible Heat) during the 2019–2024 study period.

The contours delineate the 80% cumulative contribution area (isopleth), ensuring that the analyzed fluxes originate predominantly from the target citrus orchards and minimizing the influence of surrounding distinct land covers. To characterize seasonal variability in determining the source area, the footprints are stratified by season: the irrigation season (typically March through October) and the winter season (November through February). This distinction highlights the shift in prevailing wind directions and source area contributions throughout the phenological cycle.

Fig. S1. Aggregated daily flux footprints for the Strathmore sites (EW and NS) over the 2019–2024 period. Yellow and blue indicate the irrigation (March–October) and winter (November–February) seasons, respectively. The red circle indicates the station location.

Fig. S2. Aggregated daily flux footprint for the IvanhoeEW site over the 2019–2024 period. Yellow and blue indicate the irrigation (March–October) and winter (November–February) seasons, respectively. The red circle indicates the station location.

4. S4: FORMULATION OF THE CITRUS TEMPORAL UPSCALING MODEL

Method A: Solar Irradiance-Based Algorithm This method is based on the assumption that ET is well correlated and proportional to solar radiation (R_s) [25]. The daily ET estimate ($ET_{a,A}$) is calculated as:

$$ET_{a,A} = \left(\frac{R_{s,d}}{R_{s,i}} \right) \times ET_i \quad (S1)$$

where ET_i is the instantaneous evapotranspiration (mm h^{-1}), $R_{s,i}$ is the instantaneous solar radiation (W m^{-2}), and $R_{s,d}$ is the total daily solar radiation ($\text{W m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$).

Method B: Grass Reference ET-Based Algorithm. This method, proposed by [26] based on alfalfa reference ET [27], assumes that the ratio of actual to reference ET (ET_o) remains constant throughout the day. The daily ET estimate ($ET_{a,B}$) is calculated as:

$$ET_{a,B} = \left(\frac{ET_i}{(ET_o)_i} \right) \times (ET_o)_d \quad (S2)$$

where $(ET_o)_i$ is the hourly grass reference evapotranspiration (mm h^{-1}) and $(ET_o)_d$ is the daily grass reference evapotranspiration (mm d^{-1}). $(ET_o)_i$ was calculated according to the standardized ASCE Penman-Monteith equation [28].

Method C: Citrus Temporal Upscaling Model Combination algorithm. We empirically developed a robust temporal upscaling for citrus orchards. The algorithm combines the two previous approaches with a daily-to-instantaneous air temperature ratio was also applied inspired by the [29] algorithm for daily net radiation estimation.

$$ET_{a,C} = \left(\frac{ET_{a,A} + ET_{a,B}}{2} \right) \times \frac{Ta_d}{Ta_i} \quad (S3)$$

where Ta_i is the hourly air temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) and Ta_d is the daily air temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$). Although it seems complicated, the input parameters are broadly available from numerous sources, and are the most widely used.

5. S5: JUSTIFICATION FOR THE SIMPLE AVERAGE ENSEMBLE BENCHMARK

As mentioned in the main text, a simple arithmetic average ensemble was chosen as the primary benchmark due to its superior performance and reproducibility compared to the pre-packaged OpenET ensemble product. Table S1 presents the descriptive performance metrics that support this decision. The data shows that the self-computed Simple Average yields a higher KGE and a lower NRMSE than the OpenET Ensemble, indicating a better overall model fit.

Table S1. Comparative Performance Metrics for Individual Models and Ensemble Benchmarks. The Simple Average was constructed using the six base OpenET models (DisALEXI, eeMETRIC, geeSEBAL, PT-JPL, SIMS, and SSEBop).

Model Name	KGE	NRMSE (%)	RMSE	R ²	MDMI	MAE	MBE
DisALEXI	0.63	30.0	1.0	0.48	33.0	0.8	0.5
eeMETRIC	0.55	39.4	1.3	0.43	15.1	1.0	0.7
geeSEBAL	0.64	35.6	1.2	0.56	28.8	1.0	0.8
PT-JPL	0.58	34.7	1.1	0.68	22.9	1.0	0.9
SIMS	0.74	28.6	0.9	0.67	45.3	0.8	0.6
SSEBop	0.74	28.6	0.9	0.70	45.3	0.7	0.6
OpenET Ensemble	0.68	29.5	1.0	0.75	38.5	0.8	0.8
Simple Average	0.71	27.8	0.9	0.75	43.4	0.7	0.7

6. S6: BAYESIAN MODEL AVERAGING MODEL SPECIFICATIONS

A. Probabilistic ensemble framework

To address the research questions, we developed a probabilistic ensemble framework based on Bayesian Model Averaging (BMA). Our approach was designed to systematically evaluate the competing contributions of calibration architecture and error structure specification. To achieve this, we implemented a progression of BMA models, each developed in two parallel frameworks:

- A benchmark framework assuming conditional independence among observation errors.
- A primary framework explicitly modeling spatiotemporal dependencies in the error structure.

This dual-framework design allows for a direct, comparative analysis of where predictive gains originate. Our choice to build upon the standard BMA structure, rather than using more abstract machine learning methods, was deliberate to preserve the physical interpretability of model weights and calibration parameters. All models were implemented in Stan using Hamiltonian Monte Carlo with the No-U-Turn Sampling algorithm [30–32].

A.1. Model architectures: a systematic progression of complexity

To systematically address the research questions, a suite of BMA architectures of increasing complexity was developed. Each architecture was implemented within both the conditional independence (CI) and the spatiotemporal frameworks. This section conceptually outlines the architectural variants; detailed mathematical formulations and Stan codes for all models are provided in Data availability statement (Zenodo repository).

Global calibration architectures This foundational set of models applies a single, globally consistent calibration to the entire dataset. Four variants were tested to dissect the nature of systematic ensemble error:

- Global BMA weights only: A simple weighted average ($mu = \sum w_k \cdot x_k$), establishing a baseline performance based solely on optimal model weighting.
- Global BMA intercept: An additive term (α) was included ($mu = \alpha + \sum w_k \cdot x_k$) to correct for a consistent, overall bias in the ensemble.
- Global BMA scale: A multiplicative factor (β) was included ($mu = \beta \cdot \sum w_k \cdot x_k$) to correct for proportional errors, where the magnitude of the bias depends on the magnitude of the ET prediction.
- Global BMA full: A combined model ($mu = \alpha + \beta \cdot \sum w_k \cdot x_k$) was implemented to simultaneously correct for both bias and proportional errors.

Hierarchical (site-specific) architectures To test the hypothesis that calibration needs vary systematically between locations, hierarchical (or multilevel) versions of the calibration models were developed (hierarchical intercept, hierarchical scale, and hierarchical full). In these models, the calibration parameters (α_s and β_s) were allowed to vary by site s . This was implemented using a partial pooling approach, where site-specific parameters are modeled as draws from a common population distribution [33]. This structure allows the model to learn unique calibration parameters for each site while borrowing strength across sites, providing a robust compromise between a single global calibration and fitting independent models for each location [34].

State-dependent architectures To investigate whether model performance varies dynamically with environmental conditions, two state-dependent models were developed. The first (global state-dependent intercept) allows only the intercept correction to vary with environmental conditions: $\alpha_i = \alpha_0 + \sum_{p=1}^P \alpha_p Z_{i,p}$, where $Z_{i,p}$ is the value of meteorological covariate p for observation i . The second (global state-dependent weights and intercept) extends this by allowing both the model weights and the intercept to vary as linear functions of key meteorological covariates (maximum temperature, minimum temperature, dew point temperature, solar radiation, wind speed at 2 m, and reference ET) derived from Spatial CIMIS. This state-dependent formulation tests whether adaptive, real-time calibration can provide further predictive improvements over static methods, a particularly relevant question given the known seasonal performance variations of many ET models [35, 36].

A.2. Error structure specification: from conditional independence to spatiotemporal dependence

Standard regression models often assume conditional independence: that residuals are independent after accounting for predictors. This assumption is rarely met in environmental data, where unmeasured, spatially structured covariates and temporally autocorrelated processes create strong residual dependencies [37, 38]. Ignoring spatiotemporal autocorrelation leads to biased parameter estimates, overestimated precision, and reduced predictive power [39]. For temporal data specifically, unmodeled autocorrelation misattributes variance among hierarchical levels, biasing inferences about variance components [40, 41].

To quantify the impact of these assumptions on ET model performance, two parallel model suites were developed.

Benchmark framework: an assumption of conditional independence (CI) As a methodological benchmark, a full suite of BMA models was first developed under conditional independence assumptions [42]. This framework posits that, after conditioning on all available predictors, the prediction errors (residuals) are independent of one another. In essence, it assumes that an error at one site or time provides no information about potential errors at other sites or times. While this assumption facilitates simpler modeling, it stands in contrast to the known interconnectedness of agricultural systems.

A full suite of BMA models was first implemented under conditional independence [42]. These CI models serve as an ablation study, establishing performance when data structure is ignored and enabling direct quantification of gains from modeling dependencies [43].

Primary framework: a design-based spatiotemporal approach To explicitly account for spatiotemporal dependencies, the primary framework was implemented using a multivariate Student’s t-distribution (MVT). This approach jointly models all site observations from a single day as a vector, \mathbf{y}_t , allowing the model to learn the error structure both between and within sites. This design was motivated by two mechanisms:

- **Spatial correlation:** Although study sites had non-overlapping flux footprints [24], they shared regional climatic drivers (e.g., sub-regional atmospheric patterns) known to induce spatial correlation in residuals. A prediction error at one site therefore provided information about likely errors at neighboring sites on the same day.
- **Temporal correlation:** Agricultural systems exhibit temporal memory. A first-order autoregressive AR(1) process was incorporated to model short-term persistence, acknowledging that conditions on one day influence the next. This AR(1) structure may not fully capture longer-term dependencies, such as soil moisture memory operating across seasonal timescales [44].

By using a joint likelihood, this MVT framework decomposes the total prediction error into three interpretable components:

- **Observational variance** (σ_{obs}^2): Variability from the observation process, including measurement and other independent noise.
- **Spatial variance** ($\sigma_{spatial}^2$): Spatially structured variance governed by the correlation matrix $\Omega_{spatial}$.
- **Temporal variance** ($\sigma_{temporal}^2$): Site-specific temporal variance modeled via an AR(1) coefficient $\rho_{temporal,s}$.

Spatial correlation parameterization. An unstructured correlation matrix $\Omega_{spatial}$ was estimated directly rather than using structured spatial models (e.g., Gaussian Processes, kriging) that parameterize correlation as a function of distance [45]. This approach was selected for parsimony (three pairwise correlations for three sites), flexibility (avoiding distance-based assumptions often violated by management and microclimate effects in agriculture), and alignment with study objectives (model comparison within a fixed network). A weakly informative LKJ($\eta = 2$) prior regularized estimates, permitting strong correlations only when data-supported [46].

This framework treated residual correlation as an explicit feature of the system rather than a statistical nuisance, providing an improved representation of spatiotemporal dependencies for uncertainty quantification.

Robust likelihood specification Environmental datasets frequently exhibit heavy-tailed residuals due to measurement anomalies, extreme weather events, and unmodeled processes. Standard Gaussian likelihoods are insufficiently robust to such deviations, often manifesting as sampler pathologies (e.g., divergent transitions) during MCMC estimation. To address this, all models were implemented using Student’s t-distributions as the observation likelihood. For the MVT framework, this took the form of a multivariate Student’s t-distribution; for the CI framework, it was implemented as a product of independent univariate t-distributions.

The Student’s t-distribution generalizes the normal distribution by introducing a degrees-of-freedom parameter, ν , that controls tail heaviness. This parameter was estimated from the data, allowing the model to adaptively learn the error distribution. For numerical stability and to ensure $\nu > 1$, a weakly informative $\text{Gamma}(2, 0.1)$ prior was placed on $\nu - 1$, following [47]. This parameterization improved sampler robustness.

7. S7: PRIOR SPECIFICATIONS AND MODEL IMPLEMENTATION

A sequential and empirically grounded approach to prior specification was employed, following best practices for Bayesian workflow [43]. Initial priors for simpler global models were weakly informative, centered on baseline expectations derived from exploratory data analysis but with sufficient variance to allow the data to dominate the inference. Subsequently, the posterior distributions from these baseline models were used to construct more constrained, regularizing priors for the complex hierarchical and state-dependent architectures. This iterative strategy was critical for enhancing computational stability and ensuring that all priors remained consistent with the scale of the data. The adequacy of all final prior specifications was validated via Prior Predictive Checks and are available in Data Availability. Key prior choices are summarized below.

- **BMA weights and structural parameters:** A symmetric *Dirichlet*(1) prior, representing equal initial credibility, was used for the BMA weights (w) across all models. Priors for common structural parameters, such as the spatiotemporal components (*LKJ*(2), *Beta*(3, 2)) and the robust likelihood parameter ($nu_minus_one \sim \text{Gamma}(2, 0.1)$), were held consistent to ensure a fair comparison of model architectures.
- **Global calibration parameters:** Priors for the simpler global models (global BMA intercept and global BMA scale) were specified to be weakly informative. For example, the prior for the log-transformed scale factor ($\ln(\beta)$) was *Normal*(−0.22, 0.3), which centers the median a priori scale factor at $\exp(-0.22) \approx 0.8$. This reflects a soft constraint based on the common observation of slight overestimation in satellite-ET models. The posterior distributions from these simpler variants were then used to construct empirically informed priors for the more complex global BMA full model, representing a sequential model-building process within this architectural class.
- **Hierarchical regularization priors:** Priors for the hierarchical models were specified to be intentionally more regularizing to manage their higher complexity and ensure robust sampler convergence. A sequential strategy was employed within this architectural family. For the hierarchical models with a single calibration component (hierarchical intercept and hierarchical scale), the priors for the population-level means (e.g., μ_α) were weakly informative. Crucially, the standard deviations of the site-specific effects ($\sigma_\alpha, \sigma_\beta$) were assigned strongly regularizing Half-Normal priors. Specifically, the prior for the hierarchical Intercept model was $\sigma_\alpha \sim \text{Normal}(0, 0.1)$, and for the hierarchical scale model, it was $\sigma_\beta \sim \text{Normal}(0, 0.15)$. This choice is a well-established technique to prevent sampling pathologies (e.g., divergent transitions) by enforcing strong partial pooling. Sensitivity analyses using wider priors (e.g., *Normal*(0, 0.5)) resulted in persistent sampling pathologies (divergent transitions), confirming that this level of regularization was necessary for computational stability given the limited number of sites. The final priors were validated as plausible via Prior Predictive Checks (Supplementary Material S7). The posterior distributions from these simpler hierarchical structures were then used to inform the priors for the population-level hyperparameters of the hierarchical full model. For this most complex variant, the priors on the variance components were specified as $\sigma_\alpha \sim \text{Normal}(0, 0.2)$ and $\sigma_\beta \sim \text{Normal}(0, 0.1)$, representing a balance between the information gleaned from the simpler models and the need for continued regularization. Importantly, no prior information was passed from the global models to the hierarchical models. This maintained a clear separation between

the two architectural families, ensuring that the comparison of their performance was not confounded by shared prior information.

- State-dependent priors: Priors for the coefficients of environmental covariates (e.g., α_{meteo}) were specified as regularizing zero-centered Normal distributions (e.g., $Normal(0, 0.5)$). Given that the environmental covariates were standardized, this prior reflects a default assumption that a one-standard-deviation change in an environmental driver is unlikely to shift the ensemble intercept by more than $\sim 1 \text{ mm d}^{-1}$, a soft constraint that prevents overfitting while allowing for strong effects if supported by the data.

All models were fitted using the Hamiltonian Monte Carlo with No-U-Turn Sampler. Four parallel chains were run for 4,000 iterations each, with the first 2,000 discarded as warmup. For most models, default sampler parameters were sufficient for robust convergence. However, for the most complex hierarchical variants (hierarchical scale and hierarchical full) which exhibited initial convergence difficulties, the sampler’s *adapt_delta* parameter was increased from 0.8 to 0.95 to ensure stable exploration of the posterior geometry.

8. S8: MCMC DIAGNOSTICS AND ELPD COMPUTATION DETAILS

Model validity and predictive performance were assessed through a three-stage process: (1) MCMC convergence diagnostics, (2) Pareto smoothed importance sampling leave-one-out cross-validation (PSIS-LOO-CV) for model screening, and (3) task-specific temporal cross-validation designed to respect the spatiotemporal dependency structure.

MCMC convergence diagnostics The reliability of posterior estimates was assessed using standard diagnostics. Convergence was confirmed by ensuring the rank-normalized split- $\hat{R} < 1.01$ for all parameters and effective sample sizes (Bulk-ESS and Tail-ESS) exceeding 100 per chain [48]. Models exhibiting divergent transitions underwent iterative refinement of model parametrization, prior specifications, and/or sampler settings until robust convergence was achieved.

PSIS-LOO-CV for model screening Pareto smoothed importance sampling leave-one-out cross-validation (PSIS-LOO-CV) was initially attempted for preliminary screening of model predictive performance and identification of potential influential observations [49]. For the CI framework, pointwise log-likelihoods were computed directly from the factorized likelihood (product of independent univariate Student’s t-distributions). For the MVT framework with its non-factorizable multivariate Student’s t likelihood, the efficient method for computing conditional pointwise log-likelihoods proposed by [50] was implemented.

The Pareto \hat{k} diagnostic identified a substantial number of influential observations with high \hat{k} values ($\hat{k} > 0.7$), indicating that the importance sampling approximation was unstable for these points. Stabilization of the approximation was attempted using moment matching [51], but a significant number of observations remained problematic, rendering PSIS-LOO-CV unreliable for model performance screening. Correction of these unstable estimates via exact LOO-CV (i.e., re-fitting the model for each problematic observation) was computationally prohibitive. Furthermore, for temporal data, LOO-CV allows information from future observations to influence predictions of the past, providing an overly optimistic estimate when the actual task is to predict future time periods [52]. While approximate leave-future-out cross-validation could address the temporal structure issue, it remains an importance sampling approximation and would still require multiple model refits for observations with high \hat{k} values.

Consequently, we adopted forward-chaining temporal cross-validation with an expanding window as our primary evaluation framework. This approach: (1) respects temporal ordering, (2) directly evaluates operational forecasting scenarios where models trained on historical data must predict future years, and (3) provides honest assessment of extrapolation to novel climatic conditions—the critical capability for drought-resilient water management systems.

Bayesian model comparison using fold-level ELPD Predictive performance of Bayesian models was compared using the expected log predictive density (ELPD) computed at the fold level [49]. To respect the spatiotemporal dependency structure, the ELPD calculation was decomposed over time steps while maintaining spatial correlations within each time step. For each fold, the joint log-likelihood of all observations at time step t was computed for each posterior sample $s = 1, \dots, S$, capturing the multivariate Student’s t structure with spatial correlation among sites. The log predictive density for each time step was calculated via log-sum-exp transformation

for numerical stability, and the fold-level ELPD was obtained by summing over all time steps in the held-out test set. This formulation respects spatial correlations within each time step while assuming conditional independence across time steps given the model parameters and spatiotemporal random effects.

Models were formally compared based on paired differences in fold-level ELPD values across the four folds. For each model relative to a reference model, the mean ELPD difference and its standard error were computed following [49], with the standard error calculated as $SE = \sqrt{K} \cdot SD(\Delta ELPD_{\text{fold}})$, where $K = 4$ is the number of folds and $SD(\Delta ELPD_{\text{fold}})$ is the sample standard deviation of the fold-level differences.

Several factors affect the reliability of these standard error estimates and warrant careful interpretation. First, the relatively small number of folds ($K = 4$) limits the precision of variance estimation. Second, the overlapping training windows inherent to forward-chaining cross-validation induce correlation between folds, violating the independence assumption underlying standard error calculation [53]. Third, when models have similar predictive performance (small $|\Delta ELPD|$), the distribution of ELPD differences may exhibit substantial skewness, and the normal approximation to the sampling distribution becomes poorly calibrated. These factors suggest that the computed standard errors likely underestimate true uncertainty in the fold-level ELPD differences.

Despite these limitations, all models were evaluated using identical fold assignments and held-out test sets, ensuring that paired comparisons are conducted under equal conditions. This makes the relative model ranking robust for model selection purposes. Following recent guidance on cross-validation uncertainty quantification [54], we report both $\Delta ELPD$ and SE for all model comparisons in the main text without applying fixed significance thresholds. When $|\Delta ELPD| > 4$ and sample sizes in training folds exceed 100 observations, the normal approximation is generally well calibrated. For smaller differences, models should be considered to have similar predictive performance, and selection should prioritize parsimony or theoretical considerations over statistical significance.

9. S9: CHARACTERIZING PREDICTION SIMILARITY AND ERROR STRUCTURE DIVERSITY

We quantified model diversity using distance correlation (dCor) for prediction similarity and energy distance (ED) for error pattern dissimilarity. Hierarchical clustering (Ward’s D2 linkage) identified two clusters in both analyses (Figures S3 and S4), though with different groupings: prediction-based clustering separated eeMETRIC and SSEBop, while error-based clustering grouped DisALEXI, eeMETRIC, and SEB-PV. This incongruence—models with similar predictions exhibiting distinct error structures—confirms sufficient diversity for ensemble modeling and justifies BMA’s performance-weighted approach.

Fig. S3. Hierarchical clustering based on prediction similarity (distance correlation).

Fig. S4. Hierarchical clustering based on error dissimilarity (energy distance).

10. S10: CONVERGENCE DIAGNOSTICS AND MODEL IDENTIFIABILITY

A. Convergence diagnostics

Table S2 reports detailed convergence diagnostics for all Bayesian model configurations fitted in this study. All models achieved robust convergence according to standard criteria [48]: $\text{split-}\hat{R} < 1.01$ for all parameters, effective sample sizes (Bulk-ESS and Tail-ESS) exceeding the recommended

minimum of 100 per chain (100×8 chains), and zero divergent transitions after tuning `adapt_delta` to 0.95 for hierarchical models.

Table S2. Model diagnostics and percentage decomposition of residual variance.

Model architecture	\hat{R}_{\max}^a	Bulk-ESS ^b	Tail-ESS ^b	Influential obs. ^c
<i>Global Calibration</i>				
BMA weights only	1.005	1645	2365	65 obs. ($0.5 \leq \hat{k} \leq 0.7$)
Intercept	1.006	1552	2217	3 obs. ($\hat{k} > 0.7$)
Scale	1.007	1360	1814	5 obs. ($\hat{k} > 0.7$)
Full	1.007	1481	1220	4 obs. ($\hat{k} > 0.7$)
<i>State-dependent</i>				
Intercept	1.003	2108	3601	2 obs. ($\hat{k} > 0.7$)
Intercept and weights	1.007	1525	2198	2 obs. ($\hat{k} > 0.7$)
<i>Hierarchical</i>				
Intercept	1.005	1424	2122	6 obs. ($\hat{k} > 0.7$)
Scale	1.010	1053	1671	19 obs. ($\hat{k} > 0.7$)
Full	1.003	1250	1940	10 obs. ($\hat{k} > 0.7$)

^a Maximum rank-normalized split - \hat{R} statistic; values below 1.01 indicate convergence.

^b Minimum effective sample size; values > 800 are considered adequate (100 per chain).

^c Number of influential observations identified by the Pareto \hat{k} diagnostic. Values of $\hat{k} > 0.7$ indicate that the PSIS-LOO approximation is unreliable.

B. Influential observations and PSIS-LOO diagnostics

Pareto \hat{k} diagnostics identify observations where leave-one-out approximations are unreliable ($\hat{k} > 0.7$). The hierarchical scale model exhibited the highest count ($n = 19$, 6.3% of data), reflecting parameter non-identifiability between scale factors (β_s) and model weights (w) under limited spatial replication. This correlation creates challenging posterior geometry, requiring `adapt_delta` = 0.95 for stable sampling.

We retained this natural parameterization to preserve interpretability of scale factors and weights as directly estimated quantities, accepting the computational cost as necessary for transparent parameter interpretation. Alternative parameterizations (e.g., centered vs. non-centered) were explored but offered minimal improvement given the fundamental constraint of limited spatial replication.

C. Hierarchical models under limited spatial replication

With only $n = 3$ sites, identifiability issues in hierarchical models are well-documented in the multilevel modeling literature [55]. [55, p. 275] note that with few groups, multilevel models typically provide minimal improvement over classical approaches, as the data are insufficient to reliably estimate both group-level variance and group-specific parameters.

We nonetheless implemented hierarchical architectures for comprehensive comparison, anticipating that expanded spatial coverage would be needed to realize their potential benefits. Our empirical results (in main text) confirm these theoretical expectations: with $n = 3$ sites, hierarchical models offer minimal advantage over simpler alternatives (hierarchical full vs. global full: $\Delta\text{ELPD} = 11.2$). However, we expect that with larger monitoring networks ($n > 10$ sites), hierarchical

models would demonstrate superior performance through improved parameter identifiability and effective shrinkage of site-specific estimates toward the population mean.

For the optimal state-dependent intercept model, only two observations exhibited $\hat{k} > 0.7$ (September 2, 2022 and October 25, 2024), both representing complete measured data that passed quality control protocols. These represent genuine model limitations under extreme conditions rather than data artifacts.

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